
GROWTH RESPONSE OF CLARIAS GARIEPINUS FINGERLINGS TO SELECTED COMMERCIAL FEED

*Obudulu C., Ikeh M. I., Aghalu U. C. and Olisa C. S.

Department of Zoology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Email: obuduluchibuzor@gmail.com; ikeh@unizik.edu.ng; uc.aghalu@unizik.edu.ng; cs.olisa@unizik.edu.ng

Phone Number: 08029140724

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17910252>

Abstract: This study evaluated the growth performance of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings fed with three commercial feeds: Coppem feed, Multifeed, and Vital feed over six weeks. The results showed that fish fed with Coppem feed attained the highest average weight (32.53 ± 3.62 g), followed by Multi feed (30.02 ± 3.44 g) and while Vital feed resulted in the lowest weight (23.14 ± 2.41 g). Although the mean weekly weight gains differed significantly among feeds ($F = 0.6673$, $P = 0.03$), there was no significant difference in weekly weight increase ($F = 0.9097$, $P = 0.4237$). Similarly, the final mean lengths were highest in Coppem-fed fish (17.11 ± 0.54 cm) and lowest in Vital-fed fish (14.13 ± 0.33 cm), with significant differences observed after six weeks ($F = 0.9097$, $P = 0.004$). The increase in mean length followed a similar trend, with the Coppem feed inducing the greatest growth (10.30 ± 0.14 cm). The specific growth rates were highest for Coppem (3.90 ± 0.0) and Multi feed (3.71 ± 0.0) compared to Vital feed (2.54 ± 0.0). The survival rates were 100% for the Coppem and Multifeed groups, but only 80% for the vital feed group. Proximate analysis revealed that the Coppem and Multi feeds contained higher crude protein (45%) and lipid contents, whereas the Vital feed had the highest crude fiber and moisture levels. Overall, Coppem and Multifeeds demonstrated superior growth performance and nutritional profiles, indicating their suitability for optimal production of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings

Keywords: *Clarias gariepinus*, Growth and Commercial feeds.

1. INTRODUCTION

The African catfish, *Clarias gariepinus*, is a species of significant economic importance in aquaculture, particularly in Nigeria, where it has become a staple in both local and international markets. As a hardy and fast-growing fish, *C. gariepinus* is a viable option for enhancing food security and supporting smallholder farmers' livelihoods. However, the quality of feed provided to fish fingerlings, which directly impacts their growth performance and overall health heavily influences the success of aquaculture operations (Langi *et al.*, 2024). Despite the increasing popularity of commercial feeds in Nigeria, a notable gap remains in the understanding of how different feed formulations affect the growth response of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings. Previous studies have primarily focused on the nutritional composition of feeds or the growth performance of adult fish, with limited research dedicated to this species' early life stages (Essien *et al.*, 2024; Wei *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, the dynamic nature of the aquaculture industry, characterized by the introduction of new commercial feed brands and formulations, necessitates ongoing research to evaluate their effectiveness in promoting optimal fingerling

growth. The importance of tailored feeding strategies that consider the specific nutritional needs of *C. gariepinus* at different growth stages has been highlighted (Melesse, 2023). However, empirical evidence comparing the growth responses of fingerlings to various commercially available feeds in the Nigerian context is lacking. This study aims to address this research gap by systematically assessing the growth response of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings to selected commercial feeds, thereby providing valuable insights for aquaculture practitioners and contributing to the sustainable development of fish farming in Nigeria.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

This research was conducted in the laboratory of the Department of Biological Science, Paul University Awka. Awka is at geographical coordinates 6°16'0"N and 7°3'0"E (Fig. 1). It is situated within Nigeria's tropical rainforest zone, experiencing two distinct seasons: the wet season from April to October and the dry season from November to March. The average temperature ranges from 28.5°C between June and December to 33°C from January to April (Okeke *et al.*, 2021).

Fig 1. Location of the study laboratory

2.2 Experimental design of the experiments

This study was conducted to assess the growth response of African catfish, *Clarias gariepinus*, to different commercial feeds. Three different commercial feeds were evaluated. Vital feed, Coppem feed, and Multifeed. Feeds were selected based on their nutritional composition and market availability. The study was conducted over a period of 6 weeks. Fish in three different aquariums were fed these feeds, and their growth was assessed.

2.3 Experimental Animals Used

A total of 60 African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) fingerlings with an average weight of 5.1±0.5 grams and mean length 6.5±0.3cm were procured from a certified hatchery, Sunchi integrated farms limited, Nnewi Anambra State. The fish were then acclimatized for 4 days. After acclimatization, the fish were randomly assigned to three treatment commercial feed groups, each consisting of 15 fish per group corresponding to the different feeds. Fish were fed their respective commercial feeds twice daily (morning and evening) at a rate of 5% of their body weight for the first 4 weeks, which was adjusted to 3% of body weight for the remaining 2 weeks as fish size increased. The feeds used were obtained from the market and were analyzed prior to the study for proximate composition (protein, fat, fiber, and ash content).

2.4 The Experimental Procedure

Prior to the experiment, the fishes were acclimatized to laboratory conditions for four (4) days, during which they were fed a combined mixture of the three feeds in equal proportion at 5% of their body weight. At the end of the acclimatization, the fish were randomly assigned to three plastic aquaria, each receiving 15 fish. Feeding was then suspended for 48 h before the experiment to empty the bowel of every trace of the former food used.

The fishes in each of the three treatments were kept in black circular plastic bowls with a base diameter of 60 cm and a height of 50 cm. To control predators and insects, cover nets were placed over the bowls. Fish were hand fed twice daily at 09:30 h and 15:30 h at 5% body weight.

The water used in each aquarium was obtained from the faculty of natural science reservoir and was filled to a depth of 30cm. The water was changed thrice weekly to minimize the toxic effect of feces and unconsumed food. Growth measurement involving total length and weight of fish was done weekly using a meter rule and measuring board for length and electronic balance, respectively, and Yamato lab top balance for weight.

Water quality parameters, including temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, ammonia, and nitrite levels, were monitored weekly using standard methods. The water temperature was maintained at $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, pH at 7.5 ± 0.5 , and the dissolved oxygen concentration was above 5 mg/L. Water changes of 30% were performed weekly to maintain optimal water quality.

2.6 Growth assessment

Fish were weighed weekly using a digital weighing scale (± 0.01 g) to monitor growth. The growth parameters assessed included the following:

Weight gain (WG): $\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}$

Specific growth rate (SGR): $\text{SGR (\%)} = \frac{\ln(\text{final weight}) - \ln(\text{initial weight})}{\text{duration in days}} \times 100$

Survival rate (S %) = $\frac{N_e}{N_1} \times 100$ Where N_1 = Number of fish stocked N_e = Number of fish at harvest

2.7 Statistical analysis of the data

Growth data (length, weight, and SGR) were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by a post hoc Tukey's test for pairwise comparisons when ANOVA indicated significant differences. Statistical significance was set at the 5% level to detect differences among treatment means. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS (Windows version 15.0)

2.6 Ethical Considerations

All procedures involving fish handling were conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines for the care and use of aquatic animals. The Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) approved the study prior to start.

3. RESULT

3.1 Proximate composition of commercial diets

Table 1 Proximate composition of the test diet

Feeds	Feed size	Crude proteins	Crude fiber	Fat	Ash	Moisture	Lipid
Vital	3 mm	38%	3.5%	-	-	12%	9.5%
Coppen	3 mm	45%	2.0%	13%	9.8%	-	12%
Multi	3 mm	45%	2.5%	12%	8.5%	-	12%

The proximate analysis of the various feed samples indicated that Coppen feed and Multi feed had the highest level of crude protein (45%), while vital feed had the lowest (38%). Coppen feed also had the highest level of lipid, ash, and fat, whereas Vital feed had the lowest. Vital feed had the highest level of crude fiber and moisture and Coppen feed had the lowest.

3.2 Growth performance of the tested feeds

Table 2 shows the growth performance values in terms of weight gain (g), length gain (cm), specific growth rate (SGR %day), and survival (%) of *C. gariepinus* juveniles in the different treatments.

Table 2: Growth and survival of *C. gariepinus* fed with different commercial feeds

Parameters	Coppen	Multifeed	Vital
Initials weight (g)	6.32±0.23a	6.32±0.23a	6.32±0.23a
Final weight (g)	32.53±3.62a	30.02±3.44a	23.14±2.41b
Weight gain (g)	26.21±0.55a	23.7±0.91a	16.82±0.92a
Initial length (cm)	8.41±0.53a	8.41±0.53a	8.41±0.53a
Final length (cm)	17.11±0.54a	16.97±0.35a	14.13±0.33b
Length gain (cm)	10.30±0.14a	8.56±0.15a	5.72±0.04a
SGR (percentage per day)	3.90±0.0a	3.71±0.0a	2.54±0.0b
Survival (%)	100 %	100%	80%

All values are reported as the mean standard error (\pm SE) of the mean. Figures in the same row with the same superscripts are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$). Figures with different superscripts are significantly different ($P < 0.05$)

Coppen-fed fishes had the highest average weight after six weeks (32.53±3.62g), followed by Multi-feed-fed fishes (30.02±3.44g) and while vital feed fed fishes were least (23.14±2.41g). There was a significant difference in the mean weight of fish per week for each commercial feed ($F=0.6673$, $P=0.03$, $P < 0.05$).

The highest average increase in weight of *C. gariepinus* after six weeks was recorded for the Coppen feed-fed fishes (26.21 ± 0.55 g), Multi feed-fed fishes were intermediate (23.7 ± 0.91 g), while Vital feed-fed fishes (16.82 ± 0.92 g) were the least among the commercial feeds. There was no significant difference between the mean increase in fish weight per week for each commercial feed ($F = 0.9097$, $P = 0.4237$, $P > 0.05$).

The highest average increase in length of *C. gariepinus* after six weeks was recorded for the Coppen feed-fed fishes (17.11 ± 0.54 cm), the Multi feed-fed fishes were intermediate (16.97 ± 0.35 cm), and the vital feed-fed fishes (14.13 ± 0.33 cm) were the least among the commercial feeds. There was a significant difference in the mean length of fish after six weeks for each commercial feed ($F=0.9097$, $P=0.004$, $P<0.05$).

The highest average increase in length of *C. gariepinus* after six weeks was recorded for the Coppen feed fish (10.30 ± 0.14 cm), the Multi feed fed fish was intermediate (8.56 ± 0.15 cm), and the vital feed fed fishes (5.72 ± 0.04 cm) were the least. There was no significant difference between the mean increase in fish length per week for each commercial feed ($F = 0.7633$, $P = 0.5279$, $P > 0.05$).

Coppen feed had the highest specific growth rate (3.90 ± 0.0), followed by Multifeed (3.71 ± 0.0). Vital feed had the least (2.54 ± 0.0).

The survival rate showed that fish fed Coppen feed and Multifeed had 100% survivorship, while vital feed fed fish had 80% survival.

Discussion

The growth performance, proximate composition, and survival rates of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings fed with three commercial feeds—Coppen, Multi, and Vital—over a six-week period. The findings reveal notable differences attributable to feed composition, particularly crude protein content, which significantly influenced growth metrics such as weight gain, length increase, and specific growth rate.

Proximate analysis indicated that Coppen and Multi feeds contained the highest crude protein levels (45%), which corresponded with superior growth performance compared to vital feed (38%). This aligns with the established knowledge that dietary protein is a critical factor influencing growth in aquaculture species (Wang *et al.*, 2023). Higher protein levels enhance amino acid availability, promoting muscle development and overall growth. The observed significant differences in final weight, length, and growth rate between feeds, particularly the superior performance of Coppen feed, support findings from previous studies where increased dietary protein led to improved growth parameters in African catfish (Al Sulivany *et al.*, 2024).

The lipid and ash contents were also the highest in the Coppen feed, which may have contributed to the energy reserves and mineral balance, further supporting growth. Conversely, the higher fiber and moisture levels of vital feed could have negatively impacted nutrient absorption and utilization, explaining its comparatively poorer performance. These proximate compositions underscore the importance of balanced diets with optimal macronutrient profiles for growth maximization.

Interestingly, while there were significant differences in the final weight, length, and growth rate among feeds, there was no statistically significant variation in the weekly increase in these parameters. This suggests that while overall growth differs, the rate of weekly growth remains relatively consistent across feeds, possibly indicating

that initial differences in feed quality manifest as cumulative effects over time rather than affecting short-term weekly increments.

The Copen and Multi feeds had the highest survival rates (100%), highlighting the potential influence of nutrient-rich diets on fish health and resilience. The lower survival rate (80%) of vital feed might be related to its lower protein content or palatability issues. These findings align with the literature emphasizing the role of diet quality in fish disease resistance and survival (Alafari *et al.*, 2025).

In conclusion, the study affirms that commercial feeds with higher crude protein and balanced nutrient profiles, such as Copen and Multi feeds, significantly enhance the growth and survival of *C. gariepinus*. These results reinforce recent findings that underscore the critical role of feed formulation in aquaculture productivity (Onomu and Okuthe, 2024). Future research could explore the cost-benefit analysis of these feeds and their long-term effects on fish health and production efficiency.

REFERENCES

- Alafari, H. A., Albaqami, N. M., Abd El-Aziz, Y. M., Reyad, Y. A., Eissa, E. S. H., Abdul Kari, Z., and Abd El Megeed, O. H. (2025). Effect of nanoselenium and vitamin C on the growth performance, blood health, organ histology, molecular alterations, and disease resistance of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) against *S. ferax*. *Aquaculture International*, 33(1), 65.
- Al Sulivany, B. S., Hassan, N. E., and Mhammad, H. A. (2024). Influence of Dietary Protein Content on Growth Performance, Feed Efficiency, Condition Factor, and Length-Weight Relationship in *Cyprinus carpio* during the Summer Season Egyptian Journal of *Aquatic Biology & Fisheries*, 28(2), p. 106.
- Essien, E. A., Okon, A. O., Udoinyang, E. P., Abasubong, K. P., & Akinjogunla, V. F. (2024). Comparative Assessment of the Growth Performance of the African Catfish, *Clarias gariepinus* Fingerlings fed with two commercial feeds in Nigeria *Acta Natura et Scientia*, 5(2), 160-167.
- Langi, S., Maulu, S., Hasimuna, O. J., Kaleinasho Kapula, V., & Tjipute, M. (2024). Nutritional requirements and effect of culture conditions on the performance of the African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*): a review. *Cogent Food Agric.* 2010; 10:2302642.
- Melesse, M. (2023). Dietary strategies for better production of African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) in aquaculture: A review. *African Journal of Medical Case Reports*, 11(1), 001-008
- Okeke, J. J., Obudulu, C., Mmayie, F., Udeh, N. P., Okpoko, V. O., and Ezewudo, B. I. & Okeke, P. C. (2021). Bird diversity and distribution in three land-use types in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of the National Academy of Sciences. The Bioscientist Journal*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 87-98.
- Onomu, A. J., & Okuthe, G. E. (2024). Role of functional feed additives in enhancing aquaculture sustainability *Fishes*, vol. 9, no. 5, 167.

Wang, S., Tian, J., Jiang, X., Li, C., Ge, Y., Hu, X., and Jia, Z. (2023). Effects of different dietary protein levels on the growth performance, physicochemical indexes, quality, and molecular expression of Yellow River carp (*Cyprinus carpio haematopterus*) *Animals*, 13 (7), 1237.

Wei, L. S., Rahim, M. S. A. A., Hooi, K. Y., Khoo, M. I., Nor, A. M., & Wee, W. (2024). Comparative analysis of the growth and health of juvenile African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) fed with different starch diets *Helicon*, 10(7).